

Gender Disparity in Learning Approaches and Academic Performance among Colleges of Education Students in Katsina State, Nigeria

Dr. Sani Ahmadu Gurjiya
 Tel: +2347033020360

Department of Educational Foundations, Federal University Gusau, Gusau, Zamfara State

Abstract

This study investigated gender disparity in learning approaches and academic performance among Colleges of Education students in Katsina state. Ex-post facto design was used. The study used 333 students as samples drawn from three tertiary institutions. The Revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) was adopted to measure learning approaches, while academic performance was measured by students' cumulative grade point average (CGPA). Cronbach Alpha, Spearman-Brown Coefficient and Guttman Split-Half Coefficient values of Revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) were .51, .68 and .68 respectively. The statistic used to analyze the data was t-test for independent sample. Two hypotheses were formulated and tested. The study did not find any significant difference in the academic performance of male deep learners and female deep learners approach. So also the study did not find any significant difference in the academic performance of male surface learners and female surface learners. It was recommended that teachers and college management should give proper orientation to new students about deep and surface learning approaches to studies as well as use of essay and objective test items as assessment tools throughout their programme.

Keywords: Learning approaches, deep approach, surface approach, revised two-factor study process questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F).

Introduction

Learning approaches is another emerging issue in the study of cognitive aspect of students' learning. Learning approaches show how students process information, which later influence their learning outcomes. The concept of learning approaches revealed that in every normal classroom, students are bound to either tilt towards deep learning approach, while some tilt towards surface learning with varying degree of academic performance.

Learning approaches as a concept originated from the work of two Swedish university teachers, namely; Ference Merton and Roger Saljö at the University of Gothenburg, Sweden in 1976. They theorized that students may take to a deep learning approach with a clear intention to understand the meaning of the study material and linking it to their previous knowledge and experience. On other side of the coin, some students will adopt a surface learning approach where the intention here is to memorize and reproduce the learning material without understanding (Phan, 2006). Other proponents of this theory were Entwistle and Ramsden (1983), and Biggs (1987a).

Subsequent researches revealed that for teachers to guarantee quality of learning among

students, it is necessary for them to understand students' learning approaches. Zeegers (2001) believed that research on student learning approaches at tertiary education level can be very useful for improving tertiary teaching and learning.

The concept of deep learning approach and surface learning approach have found acceptance to the study of how students process and use information in the course of their studies. Aharony (2006) observed that students taking a deep learning approach display the ability to relate new information to previous knowledge and experience in the course of their studies and subsequent assessment. Deep learners are also in the habit of studying wide range of learning materials in order to obtain broader picture of the issue under consideration. Deep learners also show inclination to search for relevant meaning for a course or material of study. They have ability of connecting learning materials with daily life and personal experience. Aharony (2006) also revealed that deep learners are often academically high achievers and maintains feelings of great satisfaction.

Surface learning approach on the other side, had characteristics which are opposite of deep learning approach. Students who take to surface learning

approach are in the habit of choosing the quickest way to complete the learning task. They acquire the learning material without necessarily understanding its meaning. When learning a material they do not show intense interest in the learning material, activity or the need to understand it completely. Surface learners are fond of learning by rote, relying heavily on memorization and not on comprehension and to be more concerned with the time needed to complete the assignment. Surface learners are mostly motivated by need to avoid failure at school and their desire to minimize effort while completing assigned tasks. In other words, the surface approach is connected to surface motivation or to extrinsic motivation (Phan, 2006 and Yong, 2010).

Students of College of Education, who comprise both male and female, are now given equal opportunity to study and acquire Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) certificate. Women and girls have now been given concession to gain admission into colleges of education. All eligible women and girls have almost automatic admission into these institutions. Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) has now been approved as the minimum teaching qualification for teaching at all levels of education (Federal Government of Nigeria, 2004). With this development, learning at tertiary level must be directed towards making students to process information, procedures, principles and skills for later use in the classroom situation.

A number of studies were carried out on gender and learning approaches by different scholars at different time across the globe. Harputlu (2011) found gender difference in academic performance on deep and surface learning approaches among Turkish university students. His studies revealed that female Turkish university students adopt surface approach score low in academic achievement compared to their male counter parts. While, male university students who score higher on deep approach did better than female students in academic performance.

In another study, Donald and Jackling (2007) did not find any significant difference between male and female Chinese and Australian university students on deep and surface learning approaches. Chan (2003) conducted a similar study on Hong Kong education students and did not observe any significant gender difference in the learning approaches of these students.

In earlier study, Lim (2004) found a slight difference among National University of Singapore students in academic performance. Male were slightly higher than female students on deep learning strategies. This was also the case on surface learning strategies.

Katsina state students performed very low in WAEC and NECO examinations in 2011 and 2012. It is these poorly performed students that are admitted into NCE I and Pre-NCE programmes of the Colleges of Education in the state. Their performance may not significantly change to any appreciative level. The learning environment and assessment tools use on influence their performance. There are complaints by employers of teachers that a particular gender performs better than the other in work performance. Therefore, there is need to investigate the difference in the academic performance of both gender on deep learning approach (DLA) and surface learning approach (SLA). These issues make the research worthwhile as it will empirically unravel the issues under investigation.

Objectives of the study

1. To find out if there is sex difference in academic performance of College of Education students of Deep Learning Approach (DLA).
2. To examine if there is sex difference in academic performance of College of Education students of Surface Learning Approach (SLA).

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant sex difference in the academic performance of Deep Learning Approach (DLA) College of Education students in Katsina state.
2. There is no significant sex difference in the academic performance of Surface Learning Approach (SLA) College of Education students in Katsina state.

Methodology

The population of this research comprised 2,523 Nigeria Certificate in Education regular students in Colleges of Education in Katsina state. Out of the population, three hundred and thirty three (333) NCE students were sampled (Research Advisors, 2006). They were drawn from NCE-Awarding Institutions of Federal College of Education, Katsina; Isa Kaita College of Education, Dutsinma and Yusuf Bala Usman College of Legal and General Studies, Daura. Multi-stage sampling technique was employed in the research. Proportionate sampling technique was used to select the participants by institution and by gender. Simple random sampling technique (hat-and-draw) was adopted in selecting the actual participants of the study.

The instrument used in this research was the 20-item Revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) developed by Biggs, Keber and Leung (2001) which was adopted. The instrument contains two sections: Section A requires participants

to provide demographic information, while Section B contains the 20-item 5-point Likert Scale loaded with deep/surface learning approaches items. The instrument was used to measure the learning approaches of NCE students of Colleges of Education in Katsina State. For reliability the Cronbach Alpha, Spearman-Brown Coefficient and Guttman Split-Half Coefficient values of Revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) were .51, .68 and .68 respectively. The content validity of the instrument was determined by panel of experts at the Department of Educational Foundations, Usman Danfodiyo University, Sokoto and at the Department of Education, Bayero University, Kano. These experts concluded that the instrument has good content validity.

Data about students' learning approaches was obtained via Revised Two-Factor Study process questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) developed by Biggs, Kember and Leung (2001). Students' academic performance records were obtained from the Office of

the Dean, School of Education, Office of the Registrar and Office of the Head of School, School of Education, for Federal College of Education, Katsina; Isa Kaita College of Education, Dutsinma, and Yusuf Bala Usman College of Legal and General Studies, Daura, respectively. The students' academic performance was assessed by the overall result the students obtained up to NCE II Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA).

The researcher used one day in each institution to administer the questionnaire with the assistance of the lecturer holding lectures at the time of the visit. The subjects were then requested to fill in and submit the questionnaire within the lecture period.

The data collected were at the interval and each of the hypotheses was tested using t-test for independent sample. The t-test statistical tool was used to analyze the data of male and female deep learners as well as male and female surface learners and academic performance. The null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant sex difference in the academic performance of Deep Learning Approach (DLA) College of Education students in Katsina state.

Table 1: Analysis of the Academic Performance of Male Deep Learners and Female Deep Learners (N = 275)

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-cal	p-value	Decision
Male Deep	191	2.6389	.82841			Accepted
Female Deep	84	2.4493	.76634	1.788	.08	

Table 1 presents the result of t-test for independent sample analysis on sex differences in academic performance among NCE students of deep learning approach (DLA). The mean scores of male deep learners ($M = 2.64$, $SD = .83$) was greater than the mean academic performance of female deep learners ($M = 2.45$, $SD = .77$), $t(273) = 1.79$, $p = .08$. This means that male NCE students used deep learning strategies more skillfully than female NCE students.

Nevertheless, the t-calculated fell below t-critical ($t\text{-cal} < 1.96$) and the p-value indicated that the difference in academic performance between male deep learners and female deep learners was not significant ($p > 0.05$). The hypothesis, which stated that there is no significant sex difference in academic performance of NCE students of Deep Learning Approach in Colleges of Education in Katsina state was retained.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant sex difference in the academic performance of Surface Learning Approach (SLA) College of Education students in Katsina state.

Table 2: Analysis of the Academic Performance of Male Surface Learners and Female Surface Learners

Variables	N	Mean	Std. deviation	t-cal	p-value	Decision
Male Surface	37	2.3141	.76482			Accepted
Female Surface	19	1.9895	.92792	1.398	.17	

Table 2 shows the result of the t-test for independent sample analysis on sex difference in the academic performance of NCE students of Surface Learning Approach. The result indicates that male surface learners ($M = 2.31$, $SD = .76$) performed better than female surface learners ($M = 1.99$, $SD = .93$, $t(54) = 1.40$, $p = .17$). The table also revealed that t-calculated was lower than t-critical (1.96). The analysis also indicated that the difference was not significant ($p > 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis, which stated that there is no significant sex difference in academic performance of NCE students of Surface Learning Approach (SLA) in Colleges of Education in Katsina state, was upheld.

Discussion of Findings

The study investigated whether there is gender disparity in learning approaches and academic performance among Colleges of Education Students in Katsina State.

The result of the first analysis did not find significant sex differences in the academic performance of male deep learners and female deep learners. Even though the result of the study revealed that male deep learners performed better than female deep learners in academic performance. The study was in agreement with the studies of Peters, Jones and Peters (2007), Lim (2004) and Harputlu (2011).

Evidence from the study indicated that male deep learners have demonstrated higher academic scores than female deep learners. The result had invariably displayed that male NCE students were motivated to adopt deep learning strategies to get higher scores in examinations more than the female deep learners. The motivation might lie in the fact that average male NCE students need to prove evidence that he really grasped the meaning of learning material before he can get higher scores. The female NCE students found under the deep learning paradigm performed below their male counterpart, was due to some cultural inhibitions and factors. Most women in higher institutions of learning from this part of the country were either married or were about to get married. Though they deep learners, but marital burden and expectation may explain why they may lag behind their male counterpart.

The second analysis of the study did not find any significant sex difference in the academic performance of male surface learners and female surface learners. However, male surface learners scored higher than female surface learners in academic performance. The result was concurrent with the findings of researchers such as Harputlu (2011), Cano (2007) regarding the higher scores of male students

over female students in academic achievement on surface approach sub-scale.

The possible explanations of the higher academic performance of male students over female students on surface approach scale may be due to the fact that male students were quick at understanding the shortest way to get through with a course. The male students seemed to use memorization of facts and procedures routinely, which ensured committing the learning materials into memory. This type of students must be aware of assessment requirement of individual lecturers and concentrate on the possible questions that were likely to come out during examinations.

It was equally possible that male surface learners were combining their studies with some form of trade. This might interfere with their studies negatively despite their need for an NCE certificate. It was no surprise therefore when examination approached these male students would adopt strategies such as memorization, relying on past question papers and limiting studies to what the lecturer provides in form of lecture notes. The female surface students may be doing the same, though not as much as those of male surface students, due to matrimonial responsibilities as many of them are married and are living off-campus.

Conclusion

From the analysis and interpretation of the data collected, the following conclusion could be made about the study.

The study had explained that male deep students used deep learning strategies more effectively than their female counterparts. This explains why they were better than female deep learners in academic performance. Moreover, male surface learners were found to be better than female surface learners in academic performance. Male surface students used certain surface strategies that assisted them to obtain higher scores than female students.

Recommendations

1. Efforts should be made by teachers and College Management to create awareness in the students about deep and surface learning approaches. Proper orientation will address the problem of misconception of what learning is at tertiary level, right from the beginning of the programme in the College.
2. Assessment techniques in colleges of education should include not only essay type of examination items, but also objective tests items. This will assist students to think reflectively and analyze all learning materials and activities. Test items

should be set to assess higher order cognitive abilities.

References

- Aharony, N. (2006). The use of deep and surface learning strategies among students learning English as a foreign language in an internet environment. *British journal of educational psychology*, 76, 851-866.
- Biggs, J. (1987a). *Student approaches to learning and studying*. Australian Council for Educational Research.
- Biggs, J., Kember, D. & Leung, D. Y. P. (2001). The revised two-factor study process questionnaire. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 71, 133-149. Retrieved on 18th November, 2010, from www.johnbiggs.com.au/pdf/ex.2factor.spq.pdf.
- Cano, F. (2007). Approaches to learning and study orchestration in high school students. *European Journal of Psychology Education*, 22 (2), 131-151. Retrieved on 1st February, 2012, from link.springer.com/article/10.10007962FB03173518.
- Chan, K. (2003). (2008). Hong Kong teacher education students' epistemological beliefs and approaches to learning. *Research in Education*, 69, 36-50. Retrieved on 15th July, 2011, from <http://repository.ied.edu.hk/dspace/handle/2260.2/5451>.
- Donald, J. & Jackling, B. (2007). Students' characteristics: A cross-cultural study. *Proceedings of the Second Innovation in Accounting and Corporate Governance Education Conference*. 30 January-February. Hobart Tasmania. Retrieved on 14th January, 2011, from <http://www.ultas.edu.au/business/facility>.
- Entwhistle, N. J. & Ramsden, P. (1983). *Understanding students' learning*. Croom Helm Ltd.
- Federal Government of Nigeria (2004). National policy on education. *Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council*.
- Harpumlu, L. (2011). Approaches to learning and academic performance of Turkish university students. *MEVLA INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL of EDUCAD`ITION (MIJE)*, 1(2), 35-43. Retrieved on 24th March, 2012, from http://www.mije.mevla.edu.tr/archive/issue12/4/mije_11_11.pdf.
- Lim, Y. L. L. (2004). How do male and female students approach learning at national university of Singapore? Retrieved on 12th April, 2013, from <http://www.cdil.nus.edu.sg/brief/v7nl/default.htm>.
- Phan, H. P. (2006). Examination of student learning approaches, reflective thinking, and epistemological beliefs: A latent variable approach. *Electronic Journal of Research in Educational Psychology*, 4(3), 577-610. Retrieved on 2nd April, 2011 from <http://www.investigation.psicopedagogical.org/revista/.../Art10141.pdf>.
- Yong, F. L. (2010). A study on the learning approaches of Malaysian students in relation to English language acquisition. *American Journal of Scientific Research*, 9, 5-11. Retrieved on 15th January, 2010, from <http://www.eurojournals.com/ajsr.h>.